

THE MULTIFACETED NATURE OF LANGUAGE

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Abstract. The article deals with the detailed information about the evolution of language. The inherent difficulty in answering the question about the evolution of language lies in the fact that there is no evidence which suggests language origin. Anthropologists believe that man has existed for millions of years. But the earliest deciphered written records are barely 6,000 years. The archeological discoveries of writing systems provide no clue to the origin of language. Writing, as the visual representation of language, has a much shorter history. Our ancestors spoke long before they wrote. Among the thousands of languages in the world today, only a few hundreds of them have written forms. Because of the problem of verification, scholars in the latter part of the 19th century, who were only interested in “hard science”, ignored or even banned discussions of language origin. In 1886, the Linguistic Society of Paris passed a resolution to ban any papers on the subject.

Keywords: *artificial language, arbitrariness, branches of linguistics, creativity, cultural transmission, diachronic study, duality, displacement.*

INTRODUCTION

We use language in most of our waking life (and sometimes in dreams, too). Language is so indispensable to us that we all tend to take it for granted. Few of us ever think what it is that allows us to talk about everything in the universe and our inner world, and to do things together with others. As a learner of a foreign

language, have you ever thought about the nature of the subject that you learn through painstaking efforts?

Probing into this question, one may understand the multifaceted nature of language. Language is many things indeed: a medium of communication, a system of code, a carrier of culture, an instrument for thinking, a glue of a community, a social institution... This multifaceted nature of language explains the fact that there is no universally accepted definition of language. Linguists must face up to this question, as language is the object of study in their research. Hundreds of definitions have been proposed in the past. We cite a few here for discussion.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Language is a system whose parts can and must be considered in their synchronic solidarity. (de Saussure, 1916)

[Language is] a set (finite or infinite) of sentences, each finite in length and constructed out of a finite set of elements. (Chomsky, 1957)

Language is a purely human and non-instinctive method of communicating ideas, emotions and desires by means of voluntarily produced symbols. (Sapir, 1921)

Each of these definitions pinpoints some aspect of the essence of language, but all have left out something. Chomsky defines language by pointing out its connotation, while Sapir's definition focuses on its function.

In broad terms, linguists agree to define language as "a system of arbitrary vocal symbols used for human communication" (Wardhaugh, 1977). This definition points out what language is basically composed of and for what purpose it is used. Yet it still leaves out some connotations and functions of language. For instance, meaning, as a component of language, is not mentioned in the definition. In addition, thinking is not touched upon in the definition, but people use language to communicate and to think. Language is composed of sounds, structure and meaning, and it is used for other purposes than communication. Language is such

a multistratal and multifunctional semiotic system that no definition can cover all the constituents, features and functions that distinguish it from other communication systems.

The above definition is based on a number of theoretical assumptions. Defined as such, language is seen as unique to human beings. In other words, it is assumed that only human beings have language. Animal communication systems (bird chirps, bee dances, dog barks, so on), are all excluded.

RESULTS

Many philosophers and linguists believe that language is unique to man.

Language is a human trait that sets us apart from other living creatures. They spell out a number of features of language, which are not found in animal communication systems.

Creativity is the first and foremost striking feature of human language. It refers to the fact that language provides opportunities for sending messages that have never been sent before and for understanding novel messages. The grammatical rules and the words of a language are finite, but the sentence is infinite. Every speaker uses language creatively. Even a child acquiring his mother tongue can put speech sounds and words into novel combinations to express meanings. This feature is not found in animal communication systems. Talking birds such as parrots can imitate human utterances, but they cannot segment the sounds and the words in the phrases they imitate and put them in a different sequence.

Results of experiments show that even animals closest in kin to human beings cannot match children in learning and using language. In the 1930s, Winthrop and Luella Kellogg raised their infant son together with an infant chimpanzee named Gua. When the boy could understand *I say what I mean* and *I mean what I say*, Gua could understand neither, although it understood some words. Several decades later, another chimpanzee, named Nim Chimsky (after the famous American linguist Noam Chomsky, who states that language is unique to human beings) was taught

American Sign Language, under careful experimental conditions, including record keeping and videotaping. After analyzing the video tapes of Nim's conversations, the researchers found that only 12% of Nim's utterances were spontaneous, and of the 88% where the teacher initiated signing, half of Nim's responses were imitations of the teacher's utterance. Children initiate conversations more and frequently as they grow older. Children hardly ever imitate in conversations. Children become increasingly creative in their language use, but Nim and other chimpanzees in similar experiments showed almost no tendency toward such creativity (Fromkin, Rodman & Hyams, 2011). Facts like these seem to suggest that creativity is a feature that distinguishes human language from communication systems of other creatures.

Language contains two subsystems, one of sounds and the other of meanings. If you are given the four English speech sounds [p], [l], [i] and [d], and asked to combine them into sequences that sound like English words, you will find [plid] and [pild] are permissible, while *[pdli], *[dpli], *[lipd], *[idlp], etc. are not. The permissible sequences sound like English words. But they are not, because they do not stand for anything. On the other hand, meanings are conveyed by certain speech sounds or sequences of speech sounds. In English, [BODY OF A DEAD PERSON] is expressed by the word *corpse*. In this case, we say the concept or the meaning is lexicalized. But there is no word to stand for the concept [DEAD PLANT]. When certain speech sounds correspond to a certain meaning, a unit of language arises. The same sounds can be recombined to mean something else. In some cases, the same sequence of sounds can mean different things (such as homophones, and polysemes). This shows that meanings and sounds make up two subsystems of language. No systems of animal communication possess this feature. The barks of a dog are not analyzable. Animal communication systems cannot be cut into segments and then be reorganized into meaningful sequences. In other words, human languages are discrete while animal communication systems are non-

discrete.

The relationship between speech sounds and the meanings they represent in the languages of the world is, for the most part, an arbitrary one. The Swiss linguists de Saussure regarded the linguistic sign as composed of signifier (sound image) and signified (referent). In his view, there is no inherent relation between the two. A building we live in with our family is called *house* in English, *maison* in French, *dom* in Russian, *casa* in Spanish. If the relationship between speech sounds and meanings were motivated (i.e. not arbitrary), the words in these languages that stand for the same thing would sound the same or similar, then people would not need to learn foreign languages.

Admittedly, there are a few words in most languages that are onomatopoeic-words of which the sounds supposedly imitate the sounds of nature. This seems to contradict arbitrariness. Nevertheless, when these words of different languages are compared, it is found that they still sound different. The English word *tick tock* is equivalent to the Chinese word *dida*, *buzz* to *wengweng*. In English, *cockadoodledoo* represents the rooster's crow, but in Russian, *kukuriku*, both are different from the Chinese expression. Based on these observations, we can say that all human languages are conventional. Most animal communications are iconic. A bee dance, for example, rather directly represents its subject matter, because a direct connection exists between the number and direction of the gyrations and the sources of nectar.

DISCUSSIONS

Language can be used to refer to things real or imagined, past, present or future. When we listen to news broadcast, we know what has happened far and wide in the world. What can be spoken is not limited by time and space, while animals can merely communicate about what happens here and now. The cleverest dog cannot bark to tell others how badly its parents were treated by their owner. This feature of languages is due to the fact that the human brain is specially

structured for language and that the brains of other species are not comparable in terms of the capacities of memory and abstraction.

Language is not merely genetically transmitted from generations to generation. Children pick up their mother tongue in the process of socialization. Animal communication systems are genetically transmitted. Admittedly, the capacity for language has a genetic basis, but the particular language a person acquires or learns is a cultural fact, not a biological fact. As language is arbitrary and conventional, a child can only acquire his mother tongue interacting with people around him.

All members of a speech community can be senders and receivers of messages. This is obviously true of all human languages, but not of all animal communication systems. Bee dances are not interchangeable; only foragers send messages. Male pheasants send messages, while female pheasants do not.

Human languages can be used to describe themselves. The language used to talk about language is called **metalanguage**. When linguists write grammars or lexicographers compile dictionaries they must use metalanguage. When we teach languages as a subject we also have to use it. No evidence exists that suggests that any other species write grammars or compile dictionaries or teach the communication system to outsiders.

The above two sections discuss what language is and what characteristics of human languages are. To understand what language is we will naturally think about what language does. **Function** is the term used to discuss the question, but the word is often used in different senses in the literature.

The word *function* is used by some grammarians to refer to *organic* or *constitutive* functions of linguistic units. In this case, function means “unit’s ‘privilege of occurrence’, in terms of its position, mobility, optionality, etc., in the unit of which it is a constituent” (Quirk et al, 1985:48). Units which may appear in the same slot in the sentence have the same syntactic function.

- (1) It has been very cold *recently*.
- (2) It has been very cold *this month*.
- (3) It has been very cold *during the past two weeks*.

The italicized parts of (1), (2), (3) are functionally equivalent, for the substitution does not harm the grammaticality of the sentences.

Function is generally used in linguistics to refer to the roles language plays in our life or in societies. Even in this sense, *function* may refer to specific roles or general roles.

The specific roles language plays fulfill an individual's purpose of communication. *Speech functions* may be an accurate term for this kind of roles. When someone steps on an English speaker's toes, he/she will utter "Ouch!" almost instinctively. Football fans sometimes cannot help, during the match, shouting to cheer the team, or even swearing at a player or the umpire. In these and many other similar cases, language helps to relieve the nervous/physical energy. It plays an emotive or expressive function. Linguists have tried to generalize speech functions and classify them into several types. But the list is hardly exhaustive.

The general roles language plays are termed **metafunctions**. A metafunction is a more abstract one, which is capable of describing innumerable specific functions. According to M.A.K. Halliday (1970), language plays three metafunctions simultaneously.

(i) The ideational function

When we use language to identify things, to think, or to record information, we use language as a symbolic code to represent the world around us. Playing this function, language serves as a medium that links a person with the world. Everything in mind exists through language. The ideational function is, then, the function language plays in human cognition, in our conceptualization of the world. It is this function of language, in a sense, that brings the world into our mind.

(ii) The interpersonal function

In addition to using language to conceptualize the world, we use it as a medium to get along in a community. We use it to identify ourselves and others, to soothe or anger someone, to argue with or to convince others, to thank or to apologize to somebody, and more importantly, to get things done together with others or by others. This function of language binds individuals together. With this function language is able to glue all members of a speech community.

(iii) The textual function

In using language, we organize messages in a logical way so that they fit in with the other messages and with the wider context in which we are talking or writing. When we speak or write we usually don't confine ourselves to single phrases or sentences: we string them together to form a text. There are expressions that refer backwards and forwards, or substitute for others, or link phrases or sentences. They play the role of bringing units of language into unity.

CONCLUSION

Last but not the least, adaptability is another essential feature of human language. It is an open system so that all social changes can be represented. Along with social progress, innovations and new products are coded by language. Concepts that originated in other cultures may be borrowed into a natural language and new words are added. That is why dictionaries must be renewed now and then. This feature is definitely not possessed by communication systems of other creatures. For example, duck's quacks remain the same all the time.

Linguists have observed other characteristics, but the ones discussed above are more striking, particularly the first one. These are universal features possessed by all human languages. Although features except *creativity* and *duality*, none is found to have all the features. On this basis linguists tend to conclude that human languages are qualitatively different from animal communication systems.

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